

A. Overview of all Rated Outlets

Table 1: Overview of all Rated Outlets

Outlet		
19th News	Fortune	RedState
ABC News	Forward	Reuters
Advocate Magazine	Fox Business	Right Wing Watch
Agence France-Presse	Fox News	Roll Call
Al Jazeera	Glamour	RT
AL.com	Glenn Beck**	Salon
AlterNet	Glenn Greenwald	Salt Lake Tribune***
American Greatness	Global News	San Diego Union-Tribune
American Independent	Good News Network	San Francisco Chronicle
American Prospect	Harper's Bazaar	SeattlePI
American Thinker**	Hartford Courant	Second Nexus***
AP	Hawaii News Now	SF Examiner
Arizona Daily Star	Heavy	SFGate
Army Times	High Country News	Shadowproof
ARS Technica	Hill Reporter	Sky News
Aspen Times	Houston Chronicle	Slate
Atlanta Black Star	HuffPost	Smithsonian Magazine
Atlanta Journal-Constitution	In These Times	Snopes
Axios	Independent Journal Review***	Sojourners
AZ Central	Indianapolis Star	South China Morning Post
Baltimore Sun	Inquisitr	Sputnik International News
BBC	Inside Climate News	St. Louis Post-Dispatch
Bearing Arms	Insider	Star Tribune-Minneapolis
Before It's News	Jacobin	Stars and Stripes
Big League Politics	Jezebel	Sun Sentinel
Bill O'Reilly	Judicial Watch	Syracuse Post-Standard
Billboard	Just the News	Talking Points Memo
Bipartisan Report**	Kansas City Star	Tampa Bay Times
Bloomberg Government**	LA Times	Tangle
Bloomberg News	LA Weekly	TechCrunch
Boing Boing*	Laconia Daily Sun***	Teen Vogue
Boston Globe	Las Vegas Review-Journal	Tennessean
Boston Herald	Liberty Nation	The American Conservative
Breitbart	Life News	The American Spectator
Bring Me the News	LifeZette	The Atlantic
BuzzFeed News	MarketWatch	The Bulwark
Capitol Weekly	MEDIAite	The Business Journals***
Cato Institute	Meidas Touch	The Christian Post
CBN	Mercury News	The College Fix
CBS News	Mic	The Dispatch
CFO	Military Times	The Economist
Charleston Gazette-Mail	Milwaukee Journal Sentinel	The Evening Times*
Chicago Sun-Times	Montana Free Press	The Federalist

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Table 1: Overview of all Rated Outlets (cont.)

Outlet		
Chicago Tribune	Mother Jones	The Guardian
Chicks on the Right	MSNBC	The Hill
Christian Science Monitor ^{***}	National Catholic Register	The Independent
Christianity Today	National File	The Intercept
Chron.com ^{***}	National Review	The Liberty Loft ^{***}
Cleveland.com	NBC News	The Nation
CNBC	New Republic	The New American ^{**}
CNET	New Statesman	The New York Times
CNN ^{**}	New York Daily News	The New Yorker
CNSNews	New York Magazine ^{***}	The Oregonian
Colorado Daily ^{**}	New York Post	The Progressive
Columbia Journalism Review	New York Sun [*]	The Right Scoop
Comic Sands [*]	News and Guts	The Root
Common Dreams	NewsBusters	The Skimm
Conservative Review	Newsday ^{***}	The Stream
Consortium News	Newser ^{***}	The Trace
Cosmopolitan	Newsmax	The Verge
CounterPunch	NewsNation Now	The Village Voice
Crooks and Liars	NewsOne	The Weather Channel
Current Affairs	NewsPunch ^{**}	The Week
Daily Beast	Newsweek	TheGrio
Daily Caller	Newsy	Time Magazine
Daily Dot	NJ.com	TMZ
Daily Herald-Chicago ^{***}	NOLA.com	Townhall
Daily Kos	NowThis News	Truthout
Daily Mail ^{**}	NPR	Turning Point USA ^{**}
Daily Signal	OAN Network	Twitchy
Daily Torch	Occupy Democrats	UPI
Daily Wire	Omaha World-Herald	Upworthy
Dallas Morning News	Orlando Sentinel	US News and World Report
Deadline	OZY	USA Today
Defense News	Palmer Report	Vanity Fair
Democracy Now	Patch ^{***}	Variety
Denver Post	PBS	Vice
Deseret News	Pittsburgh Post-Gazette	Vogue
Detroit Free Press	PJ Media	Voice of America
Detroit News	Politico	Vox
Education Week	Politicus USA	Wall Street Journal
Elite Daily	Politifact	Washington Blade
Elle	Popsugar	Washington Examiner
Engadget	Popular Information	Washington Free Beacon
Epoch Times	Poynter	Washington Monthly
Esquire	PragerU	Washington Post
FAIR	ProPublica	Washington Times
Fair Observer	Quartz	Washingtonian

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Table 1: Overview of all Rated Outlets (cont.)

Outlet		
Financial Buzz	Quillette	Western Journal
Financial Times	Radio Times	WIRED
Fiscal Times**	Rasmussen Reports	WND
FiveThirtyEight	Raw Story	Wonkette
Forbes	Real News Network	ZeroHedge
Foreign Affairs	RealClear Politics	
Foreign Policy	Reason	

Note: This Table lists all news outlets that have been rated by Ad Fontes media.

* No tweets have been posted within the dedicated time frame.

** No original tweets have been found.

*** No comments or quoted retweets have been found for all articles of this outlet.